

Patterns of Internet Usage and Their Influence on the Reading Culture of Undergraduate Students at Elizade University, Ondo State

Ugonna Vivian Ailakhu

National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja.

vailakhu@noun.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19672352>

Abstract

Internet usage has become an integral part of undergraduate academic life, providing access to diverse information resources that support learning. This study examined the patterns of internet usage and their influence on the reading culture of undergraduate students at Elizade University, Ilara-Mokin, Ondo State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was adopted, with data collected from 330 students using a structured questionnaire and analysed using frequencies, percentages, mean scores, and standard deviation. Findings revealed that students exhibited moderate internet usage, primarily for social networking, educational websites, and academic activities, while their reading culture was moderate, characterised by scheduled routines and a steady reading pace. The study further found that internet usage exerts both positive and negative effects on students' reading culture. It enhances comprehension, access to academic materials, and class participation, but also reduces planned reading time and increases distraction. The study concludes that internet usage plays a dual role in shaping undergraduate reading habits and recommends promoting structured academic internet use alongside institutional policies that encourage sustained and focused reading practices.

Keywords: Internet usage; Reading culture; Undergraduate students; Academic reading habits and Digital information resources.

Introduction

The university is an institution of learning and a centre for intellectual development, where learners from diverse disciplines acquire the knowledge and skills necessary for personal growth and societal contribution. As an institution of higher education, the university awards degrees at undergraduate and postgraduate levels and plays a vital role in advancing teaching, research, and learning (Saliu, Wankasi, Eromosele, & Olukade, 2018). A key component in achieving these objectives is the university library, whose primary function is to support academic programmes by providing access to relevant, accurate, and adequate information resources in both print and non-print formats (Quadri & Abomoge, 2013). Undergraduate students constitute the largest group of university library users. Manzoor (2010) defines an undergraduate as a student who has not yet obtained a first degree and is still undergoing formal academic training. Because undergraduates outnumber postgraduate students, their information needs require special consideration in the planning and delivery of library resources and services. These students are expected to engage in extensive reading beyond classroom instruction to support assignments, seminars, term

papers, and research projects, primarily through the effective use of library and information resources (Quadri & Abomoge, 2013). The rapid expansion of the internet has significantly transformed information access and use in higher education. As one of the most influential technological innovations of the twenty-first century, the internet has reshaped communication, education, research, and social interaction. Akidi, Agbese, and Chukwueke (2021) describe the internet as a global network of interconnected computers that allows users to access vast information resources through standardised communication protocols. Asimah and Dzogbed (2020) further characterise the internet as the “mother of all networks” for its extensive reach and its capacity to facilitate real-time interaction and knowledge dissemination.

For undergraduate students, the internet has become an indispensable academic tool. Internet access available on university campuses, in libraries, and at Information and Communication Technology (ICT) centres has enhanced students’ ability to retrieve academic materials, collaborate on research, and access supplementary learning resources such as e-books, scholarly journals, and multimedia instructional content (Longe, Adeniyi, & Aka-Nwachukwu, 2023). The introduction of the internet into academic institutions in the mid-1990s was motivated by its potential to enhance students’ academic experiences and support learning in diverse contexts (Yebowaah, 2018). Today, internet connectivity is widely available in educational institutions and private spaces, further integrating digital technologies into students’ academic lives. Internet-based learning tools, including audio-visual materials, multimedia content, and online instructional platforms, have improved information retrieval and knowledge acquisition among students (Ansary & Rakshit, 2024). The internet serves as a dynamic platform for the dissemination, exchange, and interaction of information across multiple formats, thereby enhancing academic engagement and learning efficiency (Onwukanjo & Onize, 2020).

Despite these benefits, concerns persist about the impact of internet use on students’ reading culture. Reading remains a fundamental academic activity and a critical determinant of academic success and lifelong learning. Alex-Nmecha and Horsfall (2019) emphasise that reading exposes individuals to knowledge, problem-solving skills, and intellectual development. Reading is both a mechanical and a cognitive process that requires comprehension, interpretation, and critical engagement with text (Ailakhu & Unegbu, 2017). Mariam (1991) further asserts that reading is the primary mode of learning and that comprehension is essential for effective learning and retention. Reading culture refers to the habitual and sustained practice of reading beyond immediate academic requirements. Ailakhu and Unegbu (2017) describe reading culture as the development of an intrinsic interest in reading, where reading extends beyond examination purposes to become a lifelong habit. A strong reading culture fosters critical thinking, creativity, analytical reasoning, and intellectual independence (Adeoye, Agboola, & Olademeji, 2021). However, the increasing dominance of digital content has altered traditional reading patterns, often encouraging fragmented and superficial reading rather than deep, sustained engagement with texts. Several studies have reported a decline in reading culture among Nigerian undergraduate students, attributing this trend to excessive internet use, social media engagement, and digital distractions (Adeniran, 2022; Akidi, Oyije-Agbese, & Chukwueke, 2021). Many students now prefer short, easily consumable online content over textbooks and scholarly materials, a shift that may negatively affect comprehension, concentration, and critical thinking skills. Abang (2021) observes that excessive non-academic internet use has contributed to reduced engagement with traditional reading practices and, consequently, poorer academic outcomes.

Reading becomes a culture when it is practised consistently and purposefully. However, there is growing concern that undergraduate students’ reading culture is declining due to the pervasive influence of internet technologies and social media platforms (Ojedokun & Adeyanju, 2024). While the internet provides extensive academic resources that can enhance learning, excessive use, particularly for non-academic

activities such as social networking, gaming, and online entertainment, appears to compete with traditional reading practices.

At Elizade University, internet connectivity is readily available and widely used by undergraduate students. Nevertheless, empirical evidence on how patterns of internet use influence students' reading culture remains limited. It is unclear whether internet use primarily supports academic reading or reduces engagement with sustained, critical reading practices. Given the widespread availability and use of the internet in Nigerian universities, including Elizade University, it is necessary to examine how patterns of internet use influence the reading culture of undergraduate students. Understanding this relationship is essential for developing strategies that promote balanced internet use and sustain a strong reading culture within the university environment.

Objectives

1. To examine the patterns of internet usage among undergraduate students at Elizade University.
2. To assess the influence of internet usage on the reading culture of undergraduate students.
3. To investigate the challenges associated with internet usage that may affect students' reading culture.

Literature Review

The Internet

The internet is widely recognised as a global system that enables communication and information exchange across interconnected computer networks. Manuel Castells characterises the internet as a technological infrastructure that facilitates the global flow of information and communication within the network society (Castells, 2010). Douglas E. Comer similarly describes the internet as a global network of interconnected computer systems that enables millions of computers worldwide to communicate and share information using standardised protocols (Comer, 2015). Andrew S. Tanenbaum offers a complementary perspective, defining the Internet as a vast collection of interconnected networks that enables computers and digital devices to exchange data and access information across geographical boundaries (Tanenbaum & Wetherall, 2011). Collectively, these definitions emphasise the internet as a worldwide communication system that provides users with access to diverse information resources and digital services.

Internet Usage by Students

Internet usage by students refers to the ways and frequency with which they utilise the internet for academic, social, and personal activities. In universities, undergraduate and postgraduate students increasingly depend on internet resources for research, communication, collaboration, and access to educational materials. Studies of Nigerian undergraduates indicate that university students commonly use the internet for academic assignments, project preparation, social networking, and browsing educational resources, although patterns of use vary with academic needs and digital literacy levels (Edem & Ofre, 2010). Quadri and Abomoge (2013) examined the reading and internet usage habits of undergraduate students in selected Nigerian university libraries and found that internet use has become integrated into students' daily academic routines. In many cases, online searching and digital resources are gradually replacing traditional information sources such as printed books and journals. Consequently, internet usage

among students has become a central aspect of learning, information seeking, and knowledge acquisition in contemporary higher education institutions.

Reading

Reading is generally understood as a cognitive and interpretative activity through which individuals derive meaning from written symbols. It is a process of looking at a series of written symbols and deriving meaning from them (Mkandawire, 2018). According to Olanlokun (1999), reading involves the interaction between the eyes and the mind in interpreting and evaluating written texts. In this sense, reading goes beyond the simple recognition of words; it requires comprehension and the reader's ability to connect personal experiences and prior knowledge with the author's message. Okoro (2004) emphasised that children should be introduced to reading at an early age, even before formal schooling, as early exposure helps cultivate enjoyment, intellectual development, and a lasting appreciation for literature and learning. Reading is a crucial skill for learners to succeed in education and is often described as both a mechanical and an intellectual process that encourages critical thinking and understanding (Nasri & Biria, 2016; Mkandawire, 2018).

Reading Culture

Reading culture plays an important role in academic achievement and national development. Ailakhu and Unegbu (2017) established that reading culture is the inculcation of reading habits across all aspects of human life, not just for school purposes. They opined that, as a culture, reading has declined over the past years, and students are found wanting in reading daily newspapers and magazines, let alone novels or literature. This has resulted in poor reading acquisition and a lack of a strong reading culture. Anyachebelu, Anyaemene and Adebola (2011) observed that reading enhances learning, improves academic performance, and equips individuals with the knowledge required for self-reliance and societal contribution. In schools, libraries serve as important institutions for promoting reading culture by providing access to books and other information resources. Pedro and Dolapo (2023) noted that reading culture is a positive habit necessary in human societies. It contributes to critical literacy, which in turn contributes to national development. Teachers play a particularly important role by modelling positive reading behaviours and encouraging independent reading, storytelling, and reading aloud among students (Nnam, 2003; Trelease, 2005). When schools provide conducive reading environments and supportive policies, students are more likely to develop a lifelong reading habit and an appreciation for knowledge (Ailakhu & Unegbu, 2017).

The Influence of Internet Usage on Reading Culture

Empirical studies of student populations reveal mixed effects of internet use on reading culture. On the positive side, internet access expands access to diverse reading materials, including e-books, academic journals, and educational websites, thereby enhancing comprehension and research capabilities. Students who use the internet purposefully for academic work often develop improved reading practices through engagement with scholarly content online (Quadri & Abomoge, 2013). Several studies report that internet use, especially for social media and entertainment, can reduce planned reading time and distract students from deep reading. For instance, Adeleke et al. (2021) examined social media use patterns and their perceived effects on students' reading culture in selected tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria, and found that extensive social media use was associated with reduced time allocated to library and traditional print reading. Nwokeocha, Akpan, and Brown (2025) note that students increasingly prefer immediate, surface-level online content over the longer, more analytical reading required for academic study.

Role of Academic Libraries in Promoting Reading Culture

Academic libraries play a pivotal role in fostering reading culture among university students. Libraries provide access to a wide range of information resources, both print and electronic, and create an environment that encourages reading and research. They facilitate literacy by organising reading programs, information literacy instruction, reading clubs, displays, and collection development to meet diverse academic needs. (Sudan, 2023) show that libraries support reading culture through structured access to books, journals, e-resources, and spaces conducive to focused study. Academic librarians also guide students in selecting appropriate reading materials and help them navigate digital resources effectively. Despite increasing reliance on online information, the physical and digital academic library remains relevant as a centre for sustained reading and scholarly engagement (Samsuddin, Masenwat, & Ab Llah, 2021).

Theoretical Framework and Relevance to the Study

This study is based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Fred D. Davis in 1989, which explains how people adopt and use new technologies. TAM is widely used in research on the adoption of information and communication technologies in educational and informational settings. It suggests that the acceptance and actual use of a technology are mainly driven by two key factors: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Perceived usefulness is the extent to which a person believes that a technology will improve their performance, while perceived ease of use is the extent to which they find using the technology effortless (Davis, 1989). These factors influence users' attitudes, which shape their intention to use the technology and ultimately determine their actual usage. In this study, which explores internet usage patterns and their impact on undergraduate students' reading culture, TAM offers a useful perspective on the behavioural factors influencing students' engagement online. The internet, a readily accessible platform, provides quick access to information resources, electronic resources, university library repositories, and communication tools.

The relevance of TAM here lies in its ability to explain how students' perceptions of the internet affect their usage behaviours and, in turn, their reading culture. Easy and frequent access to online resources may promote digital reading habits, such as using e-books, online journals, and educational websites. Conversely, heavy reliance on internet-based sources might shift traditional reading patterns away from printed texts and library materials. The model clarifies the link between the adoption of internet technology and behavioural outcomes related to reading culture among undergraduates. It offers a conceptual foundation for examining how perceived benefits and ease of use influence how often, why, and in what ways students engage online. These engagement patterns could either support academic reading and information literacy or diminish deep, sustained reading practices. Through TAM, this study aims to understand how internet technology acceptance and usage shape the reading culture of undergraduates in today's digital learning environments.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey design because it characterises the population by outlining the features of the research problem and analysing the relationship between two variables without requiring manipulation. The target population consisted of undergraduate students at Elizade University, Ilara-Mokin, Ondo State, Nigeria. According to the university's Academic Planning Unit (2025), there were 2,300 undergraduates enrolled in the 2024/2025 academic year. A simple random sampling technique was used, ensuring each student had an equal chance of selection. To determine the sample size, Yamane's

formula (1967) was applied, which is suitable for large populations with simple random sampling. With a population of 2,300 and a 5% margin of error, the sample size was calculated as: $n = 2300/1+2300(0.05)^2 = 2300/1+2300(0.0025) = 2300/1+5.75 = 2300/6.75$ 341 respondents, rounded to the nearest whole number. Consequently, the study's sample size was 341, drawn from a total population of 2300. Data collection was conducted using a self-administered questionnaire with closed-ended items. Participation was voluntary, and respondents' confidentiality was guaranteed. The instrument was reviewed by two library and information science experts and pretested with 15 students from the Federal University of Technology, Akure, to improve clarity and coherence. The reliability of the Likert-scale items was confirmed using Cronbach's alpha, which showed high internal consistency. Quantitative data were analysed with descriptive statistics, including frequencies, means, and standard deviations, to summarise the results.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Distribution of Undergraduate Students at Elizade University.

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	145	43.9%
	Female	185	56.1%
Age	15–20 years	85	25.8%
	21–25 years	170	51.5%
	26–30 years	45	13.6%
	31–35 years	18	5.5%
	36 years and above	12	3.6%
Marital Status	Single	310	93.9%
	Married	20	6.1%
Level	100 Level	65	19.7%
	200 Level	70	21.2%
	300 Level	75	22.7%
	400 Level	60	18.2%
	500 Level	60	18.2%
Faculty	Faculty of Basic and Applied Sciences (FBAS)	75	22.7%
	Faculty of Law (FLAW)	70	21.2%
	Faculty of Engineering (FENG)	60	18.2%

Faculty of Humanities, Social and Management Sciences (FHSMS)	70	21.2%
Faculty of Agricultural and Health Sciences (FAHS)	55	16.7%

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The respondents comprised slightly more females (56.1%) than males (43.9%), indicating a minor gender imbalance. Most were aged 21–25 years (51.5%), followed by 15–20 (25.8%) and 26–30 years (13.6%), with fewer aged 31–35 (5.5%) and 36 and above (3.6%), reflecting a predominantly youthful population. The vast majority were single (93.9%), with only 6.1% married. Academic levels were fairly evenly distributed, with 300-level students (22.7%), 200-level (21.2%), 100-level (19.7%), and both 400- and 500-levels (18.2%). Balanced faculty representation ensured adequate disciplinary diversity, enhancing the generalisability of the findings to the undergraduate population at Elizade University.

Table 2: Patterns of Internet Usage among Undergraduate Students at Elizade University

Internet Usage Pattern	SA		A		D		SD		Mean	STD
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
I use the internet several times per day	99	30.0	98	29.7	81	24.5	52	15.8	2.74	1.054
I use the internet mainly for scholarly purposes	97	29.4	84	25.5	96	29.1	53	16.1	2.68	1.062
My internet usage has increased dramatically in the last year	94	28.5	89	27.0	89	27.0	58	17.6	2.70	1.032
I typically access the internet late at night or in the evening	97	29.4	102	30.9	79	23.9	52	15.8	2.75	1.010
I frequently encounter issues with internet reliability	95	28.8	91	27.6	92	27.9	52	15.8	2.72	1.053
I often utilise social networking services like Whatsapp, Instagram, and Tiktok	91	27.6	102	30.9	84	25.5	53	16.1	2.78	1.052

I use educational websites like google scholar and e-journals	89	27.0	103	31.2	87	26.4	51	15.5	2.75	1.014
I typically use my smartphone to access the internet	91	27.6	87	26.4	95	28.8	57	17.3	2.66	1.052
I generally use the internet at my hostel or home	91	27.6	106	32.1	84	25.5	49	14.8	2.78	1.071
I spend almost 4 hours a day on the internet	99	30.0	100	30.3	79	23.9	52	15.8	2.74	1.054
Weighted mean									2.73	1.053

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The findings show that internet usage among undergraduate students at Elizade University, Ilara-Mokin, follows a consistent pattern shaped by both convenience and social interaction. Students mainly access the internet from hostels or homes, with social networking platforms being the most frequently used. Academic activities, such as consulting Google Scholar and e-journals, are also common, often during evening or late-night hours, reflecting the flexibility of digital learning. Students spend an average of four hours online daily, highlighting the central role of the internet in their routines. Despite this high engagement, challenges such as unreliable connectivity persist. Overall, while internet use supports both academic and social needs, usage patterns vary moderately, emphasising the importance of accommodating diverse digital learning and recreational demands.

Table 3: Influence of Internet Usage on Reading Culture of Undergraduate Students

Internet Influence	SA		A		D		SD		Mean	STD
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
It enhances my reading culture	106	32.1	105	31.8	100	30.3	19	5.8	2.90	0.921
It makes me active in class	107	32.4	102	30.9	95	28.8	26	7.9	2.88	0.957
It increases my reading attention span	104	31.5	103	31.2	99	30.0	24	7.3	2.87	0.944
The Internet exposes me to unimportant articles and write-ups	101	30.6	104	31.5	98	29.7	27	8.2	2.85	0.954
Internet articles motivate me to read	105	31.8	102	30.9	94	28.5	29	8.8	2.86	0.968
It helps me to have a better understanding of what I am reading	104	31.5	103	31.2	101	30.6	22	6.7	2.88	0.935

Chatting with friends keeps me awake to read in the night	99	30.0	98	29.7	93	28.2	40	12.1	2.78	1.010
The Internet distracts my reading	99	30.0	109	33.0	96	29.1	26	7.9	2.85	0.942
Internet affects my academic performance	105	31.8	88	26.7	115	34.8	22	6.7	2.84	0.954
It reduces the time I plan for reading	112	33.9	104	31.5	89	27.0	25	7.6	2.92	0.953
Weighted mean									2.86	0.954

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The findings reveal that undergraduate students perceive internet use as significantly impacting their reading culture. The highest-rated item, “It reduces the time I plan for reading” ($\bar{x} = 2.92$), suggests that while students benefit from online resources, managing reading time remains a challenge. Simultaneously, items such as “It enhances my reading culture” ($\bar{x} = 2.90$), “It makes me active in class” ($\bar{x} = 2.88$), and “It helps me better understand what I am reading” ($\bar{x} = 2.88$) indicate that students view the internet as a valuable tool for comprehension and academic engagement. However, they also acknowledge its distracting aspects, including “The internet distracts my reading” ($\bar{x} = 2.85$) and “It exposes me to unimportant articles” ($\bar{x} = 2.85$). The lower rating for “Chatting with friends keeps me awake to read at night” ($\bar{x} = 2.78$) suggests that social interactions offer limited benefit for sustained reading. Overall, a weighted mean of 2.86 (SD = 0.954) confirms that students recognise both the supportive and disruptive effects of internet use on their reading habits, with moderate variation in experiences.

Table 4: Challenges Associated with Internet Usage That May Affect Students’ Reading Culture

Challenge	SA		A		D		SD		Mean	STD
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Slow internet connection (takes too long to load pages)	138	41.8	122	37.0	70	21.2	00	00	3.21	0.768
Lack of a constant electricity supply	119	36.1	128	38.8	83	25.2	00	00	3.11	0.776
Restricted access to certain networking sites	120	36.4	138	41.8	72	21.8	00	00	3.15	0.750
Very little training on how to use the internet facilities	129	39.1	122	37.0	77	23.3	2	0.6	3.15	0.793
Inadequate user skills	129	39.1	115	34.8	85	25.8	1	0.3	3.13	0.804
High cost of browsing	119	36.1	139	42.1	72	21.8	00	00	3.14	0.748
Overload of information	130	39.4	133	40.3	67	20.3	00	00	3.19	0.750

Inadequate information retrieval skills	117	35.5	121	36.7	92	27.9	00	00	3.08	0.793
Inadequate internet access in school	145	43.9	110	33.3	75	22.7	00	00	3.21	0.790
Weighted Mean									3.15	0.777

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The findings indicate that undergraduate students at Elizade University encounter multiple internet-related challenges that adversely affect their reading habits. The most prominent issues were slow internet connectivity and limited on-campus access ($\bar{x} = 3.21$), highlighting infrastructural constraints as major barriers to effective academic use. Other significant challenges included information overload ($\bar{x} = 3.19$), restricted access to certain networking sites ($\bar{x} = 3.15$), and insufficient training in using internet facilities ($\bar{x} = 3.15$), reflecting difficulties in navigating online content and limited technical competence. Additional concerns, such as high browsing costs ($\bar{x} = 3.14$), inadequate user skills ($\bar{x} = 3.13$), and limited information retrieval abilities ($\bar{x} = 3.08$), further constrain students, particularly those with lower financial resources or digital proficiency. An overall weighted mean of 3.15 ($SD = 0.777$) confirms general agreement with these challenges, underscoring the need to address infrastructural, technical, and skill-related factors to enhance effective internet use for reading and academic development.

Discussion of Findings

This study provides insight into the evolving relationship between internet usage and reading culture among undergraduate students at Elizade University, Ilara-Mokin, highlighting how digital engagement shapes academic behaviours.

Patterns of Internet Usage Among Undergraduate Students at Elizade University

Undergraduate students demonstrated high internet engagement, with a weighted mean of 2.73. Peak usage occurred at home or in hostels (mean = 2.78), primarily through social networking platforms (mean = 2.78), reflecting the prevalence of mobile and personalised access. These findings align with Jegede and Owolabi (2020), who observed that students in private universities rely heavily on mobile data due to limited campus infrastructure, and with Ojo and Akande (2019), who identified smartphones as the preferred device for Nigerian undergraduates. Frequent use of platforms such as WhatsApp, TikTok, and Instagram supports Iroghama and Egbokhare (2022), while evening and late-night browsing (mean = 2.75) aligns with Olowu and Adesina (2021), indicating that academic engagement often occurs outside traditional study hours. The reported increase in usage over the past year (mean = 2.70) reflects post-COVID-19 trends in digital learning (Ayoola & Emefiele, 2021). Overall, students are part of a broader national shift toward digital engagement, although the academic benefits remain mixed.

Influence of Internet Usage on The Reading Culture of Undergraduate Students

Students demonstrated moderate engagement with academic reading (weighted mean = 2.68). Reading 12–15 pages per hour (mean = 2.76) was common, whereas preference for library-based reading was lower (mean = 2.61), supporting the findings of Salawu and Alabi (2018) and Ekwelem and Igwe (2020) regarding the shift toward screen-based reading. Reading primarily during exams (mean = 2.65) and for less than two hours daily (mean = 2.67) reflects a utilitarian approach that limits critical thinking (Obikeze & Nwachukwu, 2019; Nnadozie et al., 2021). Preference for quiet spaces (mean = 2.62) underscores the role of the environment in reading habits (Alausa & Ogunyemi, 2020). Overall, reading remains largely obligation-driven rather than curiosity-driven.

Challenges Associated with Internet Use that May Affect Students' Reading Culture.

Students encountered significant barriers, with an overall mean of 3.15. Inadequate internet access and slow connections (mean = 3.21) highlight infrastructural limitations (Oluwadare & Akintoye, 2022), while information overload (mean = 3.19), limited digital skills (mean = 3.13), lack of training (mean = 3.15), restricted access (mean = 3.15), and high costs (mean = 3.14) point to skill- and resource-related challenges (Anunobi & Udem, 2020; Njoku & Aliyu, 2021). Persistent electricity issues (mean = 3.11) further constrain effective usage (Okonkwo & Oboh, 2020). These findings indicate that despite high digital engagement, infrastructural, technical, and skill-related limitations restrict students' effective use of online resources for reading and academic purposes.

Conclusion

Internet use among undergraduate students at Elizade University has both positive and negative effects on their reading culture. On the positive side, it improves comprehension, enhances class participation, and provides easy access to a wide range of academic resources that support the university community in conducting research, completing assignments, and meeting information needs. Excessive internet use can also reduce the time devoted to planned reading by encouraging distractions and exposing students to irrelevant online content. Although students' access and use of the internet assist them with their research, assignments, and news updates, a significant portion of their online activity is dominated by social media and content creation, which has gradually reshaped reading culture towards shorter, more interest-driven formats rather than sustained academic reading. A good number of undergraduate students rely heavily on mobile devices and social media platforms for internet access, often outside traditional study hours, and their reading culture tends to be moderate and largely examination-driven. This situation is further influenced by infrastructural, technical, and skill-related challenges. Internet usage exerts a dual impact on students' reading culture, providing academic benefits while also creating behavioural risks, highlighting the need for targeted support to sustain effective reading practices.

Recommendations

1. *Improvement of Campus Internet Infrastructure and Access:* Elizade University should invest in reliable, high-speed internet infrastructure across campuses and hostels to support its students' academic activities. Providing stable Wi-Fi access points and improving the electricity supply will reduce students' overreliance on personal mobile data and enhance their ability to access scholarly resources effectively.
2. *Promotion of Academic Use of Social Media and Online Platforms:* Since undergraduates frequently use social networking platforms such as WhatsApp, TikTok, and Instagram, the university management and lecturers at Elizade University should integrate academic discussions, reading materials, and course updates into these platforms. This will help redirect part of students' online engagement toward academic learning and information sharing.
3. *Encouragement of Consistent Reading Habits Beyond Examination Periods:* Lecturers and academic advisers of respective departments and programmes should encourage their students to cultivate a sustained reading culture rather than limiting reading to examination periods. Structured reading assignments, recommended reading lists, and regular academic discussions can help promote deeper engagement with course materials and improve critical thinking.
4. *Strengthening the Role of University Libraries in Supporting Digital Reading:* The University library should expand access to its repository and also provide quiet and conducive reading spaces.

The library staff, especially the academic librarians, should organise reading promotion programmes and instructional sessions to guide students in effectively using digital resources for academic reading.

5. *Implementation of Digital Literacy and Information Skills Training*: The university management should organise regular training programmes that equip students with digital literacy and information navigation skills. Such programmes will help students manage information overload, evaluate credible online sources, and use internet resources more effectively for academic reading and research.

References

- Abang, Y. (2021). Reading habits among students in the digital era: Changes of trends and behaviours. *Journal of Academic Library Management (AcLiM)*, 1(1).
- Adeniran, A. M. (2022). Social media and the decline of reading culture among Nigerian undergraduates. *Nigerian Journal of Communication Studies*, 10(1), 87–102.
- Adejimo, Y. A., Ilo, H. M., & Audu, P. O. (2021). The role of school libraries in promoting reading culture among secondary school students in Benue State. *Library Philosophy and Practice*.
- Adeleke, R. T., Adegboire, A. M., Babarinde, B. A., Adekunjo, O. A., & Oluwaniyi, S. A. (2021). Social media use patterns and their perceived effects on the reading culture of students in selected tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. *University of Ibadan Journal of Library and Information Science*, 4(1). <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1382-831X>
- Adekunmisi, S. R., Ajala, E. B., & Iyoro, A. O. (2013). Internet access and usage by undergraduate students: A case study of Olabisi Onabanjo University, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*.
- Adeoye, O. A., Agboola, F. K., & Oladimeji, T. A. (2021). The impact of internet usage on academic performance and reading habits among Nigerian students. *Journal of Educational Development*, 15(3), 45–57.
- Adesulu, D., Adewole, A., & Amos, R. (2017). Reading culture: How students waste hours on social media. *Vanguard*. <https://www.vanguardngr.com>
- Adeyemi, A. A. (2021). Promoting reading culture: The role of stakeholders and ICT for societal development. *Indian Journal of Library Science and Information Technology*, 6(1), 4–8. <https://doi.org/10.18231/j.ijlsit.2021.002>
- Ailakhu, U. V., & Unegbu, V. E. (2017). Librarians' promotion of reading culture and students' responsiveness in selected secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Ebonyi Journal of Library and Information Science*, 4(1), 30–42.
- Ajanaku, O. J. (2019). Utilisation of the internet by undergraduate students of the University of Ibadan, Nigeria. *International Journal of Science and Technology Education Research*, 10(3), 30–36.
- Akidi, J. O., Agbese, F. A. O., & Chukwueke, C. (2021). Influence of the use of the internet on the reading culture of students of Government College, Umuahia, Abia State, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, Article 5013, 11–13.
- Alex-Nmecha, J. C., & Horsfall, M. N. (2019). Reading culture, benefits, and the role of libraries in the 21st century. *Library Philosophy and Practice*.

- Almarabeh, T., Majdalawi, Y. K., & Mohammad, H. (2016). Internet usage, challenges, and attitudes among university students: A case study of the University of Jordan. *Journal of Software Engineering and Applications*, 9, 577–587.
- Amponsah, K. D. (2022). The impact of internet usage on students' success in selected senior high schools in Cape Coast metropolis, Ghana. *European Journal of Educational Sciences*, 9(2), 1–18.
- Amy, P. A., & Oliver, E. D. (2020). Internet usage and its effect on the lifestyle of university students. *Information and Knowledge Management*, 10(7).
- Anyachebelu, F., Anyamene, A. & Adebola, H. (2011). Strategies for promoting reading skills for the educational development of learners in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 2(4), 211 – 215.
- Ariffin, R. (1992). Definition of reading. *UK Essays*. <https://www.ukessays.com>
- Asibi, I. J., Ufuoma, E., & Alexis, U. (2021). Decline in reading culture in some selected university libraries in South-East Nigeria. *Archival and Information Science*, 10.
- Asif, M., & Yang, L. (2021). An investigation of the reading culture: The role of libraries to promote reading culture in Pakistan. *Journal of Language and Cultural Education*, 9(3), 40–62.
- Asokan, L., & Dhanavandan, S. (2013). Reading habits of newspapers among engineering professionals: An analytical study. *International Journal of Library and Information Studies*, 3(4), 36–41.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319–340.
- Edem, M. B., & Ofre, E. T. (2010). Reading and internet use activities of undergraduate students of the University of Calabar, Calabar, Nigeria. *African Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science*, 20(1), 11–18.
- Longe, O., Adeniyi, S., & Aka-Nwachukwu, V. (2023). Relationship between the use of the internet and the reading culture of secondary school students in Lagos State. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 12(1), 126–134.
- Manzoor, S. (2010). Factors conducive for the purposeful use of libraries among university students in Pakistan. *International Journal on New Trends in Education and Their Implications*, 1, 1309–6249.
- Mkandawire, S. B. (2018). Literacy versus language: Exploring their similarities and differences. *Journal of Lexicography and Terminology*, 2 (1), 37–55.
- Nasri, M. & Biria, R. (2016). Integrating multiple and focused strategies for improving reading comprehension and L₂ lexical development of Iranian intermediate EFL learners. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics and English Literature*. 6(1), 311–322.
- Nnam, J. (2003). Promoting the reading culture in secondary schools: A case study of Mengo Senior School. Unpublished dissertation, East African School of Library and Information Science, Makerere University, Kampala.
- Nwokeocha, I. M., Akpan, U. A., & Brown, G. N. (2025). Influence of social media on the reading culture of students in selected secondary schools in Oron. *Indiana Journal of Arts & Literature*, 6(8), 11–16.
- Okoro, C.C. (2004). My people are destroyed: The effects of lack of knowledge on the academic performance of Nigerian children. *Owena Journal of Library and Information Science*, 1. (1), 13 - 17.
- Olanlokun, S.A. (1999). Strategy for effective reading environment for the Nigerian Society. *Gateway Library Journal*, 2, 1–8.
- Pedro, A. K., & Dolapo, A. I. (2023). Revamping the reading culture and critical literacy of Nigerians through literature. *Mizoram University Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 9(1), 79–90.

- Quadri, O., & Abomoge, S. (2013). A survey of reading and internet use habits among undergraduate students in selected university libraries in Nigeria. *Information and Knowledge Management Journal*, 3(11).
- Saliu, U. A., Wankasi, A. J., Eromosele, G. O., & Olukade, A. O. (2018). Leadership styles and motivation on job performance of library personnel in public university libraries in North Central Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1–25.
- Samsuddin, S. F., Masenwat, N. Z., & Ab Llah, L. (2021). Systematic literature review on cultivating reading culture in academic library initiatives. *Journal of Academic Library Management (AcLiM)*, 1(2), 56.
- Sudan, R. (2023). The role of libraries and librarians in promoting reading culture among students. *JournalNX: A Multidisciplinary Peer-Reviewed Journal*, 9(6), 69.
- Toker, A., & Aminou, S. (2019). A study on reading habits of university students in Nigeria: A case of selected students of the Economics Department at Nile University of Nigeria. *The European Educational Researcher*, 2(3), 209–221.
- Trelease, J. (2005). *The Read-Aloud Handbook*, 6th edition. New York. Penguin Books.
- Venkatesh, V., & Davis, F. D. (2000). A theoretical extension of the Technology Acceptance Model: Four longitudinal field studies. *Management Science*, 46(2), 186–204.
- Yebowaah, F. A. (2018). Internet use and its effect on senior high school students in the Wa Municipality of Ghana. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, Article 1817.